

FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGY COMPANIES AND SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES: A TRANSFORMATIVE RELATIONSHIP

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of financial technology on the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Ogun State, Nigeria, focusing on financial inclusion, access to financial services, and business growth. A quantitative survey design was adopted using a sample of 300 registered SME operators drawn from a population of 1,200 through simple random sampling. Data were collected via a structured Likert-scale questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and ANOVA. The results indicated that financial technology adoption has a significant positive effect on SME performance ($R^2 = 0.64$, $p < 0.05$), explaining 64% of the variation in business performance. Similarly, financial technology significantly improves access to financial services ($R^2 = 0.58$, $p < 0.05$), while emerging financial technologies positively influence financial inclusion ($R^2 = 0.61$, $p < 0.05$). The ANOVA results further confirm that the regression models are statistically significant. The study concluded that financial technology is a key driver of SME growth and inclusion in Nigeria and recommends policies that promote digital financial adoption and infrastructure development.

Keywords: Financial technology, SMEs, financial inclusion, business performance, Nigeria.

Introduction

Small and Medium Enterprise (SMEs) are major drivers of global economic growth significantly influencing revenue, employment, production and consumption, promoting creativity and innovation through the provision of goods and services for the good of humanity. The challenges of funding, however, continues to be a significant obstacle. Financial technology Companies (FinTech) intervention has emerged as trailblazing entities, providing a range of services that include payment platforms, digital lending, and blockchain-based transactions. (Arner *et al.*, 2020).The financial landscape has been profoundly transformed by fintech companies, especially for SMEs. Accessing financial services has posed many challenges for traditional SMEs, such as lack of credit facilities, expensive transaction costs, and complex banking processes. However, by offering cutting-edge technologies that improve financial inclusion, business efficiency, and growth prospects, FinTech has completely changed the face of SME operations. (Akanbi, Oladejo and Oyeleye, 2022).

Facilitating financial inclusion is one of FinTech's most significant contributions to SMEs. The strict lending requirements of traditional financial institutions frequently make it difficult for SMEs to get finance. FinTech companies have significantly improved SMEs' access to financing by providing online credit services, peer-to-peer (P2P) lending platforms, and alternative funding possibilities (Chen *et al.*, 2019). By offering flexible loan options with expedited approval procedures, alternative financial service providers like Kabbage, Funding Circle, and PayPal Working Capital assist SMEs in meeting their capital requirements(Zhang *et al.*, 2021).

Efemena, Augustine and Ariyibi (2024) argued that FinTech innovations overtime have reduced operational costs, increased and improved efficiency of SMEs. Online payment platforms like Square and Stripe enable instant transaction processing at a reduced cost compared to traditional banking services (Puschmann,2017). Additionally, financial and accounting management software supported by FinTech, like QuickBooks and Xero, enable SMEs to automate records, bookkeeping, invoicing, and tax reporting processes, hence increasing financial management while decreasing administrative loads (Gomber *et al.*, 2018).FinTech platform in collaboration with e-commerce platform have increased SMEs marketing network, Mobile payment enriched customer's satisfaction and continuous patronage (Arner *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, FinTech has aided SMEs to rank and prioritized it customers, maintain price stability and enjoy continuous relationship and harmonize feedbacks.

Despite the immense benefits of SME's, they are however, still confronted and struggling with challenges ranging from poor financial literacy, inadequate information communication and technology (ICT) Infrastructure, internet fraud and

cybersecurity risks, exuberant technology adoption, compliance and regulatory issues, challenges Integrating with present business systems and poor awareness of FinTech Opportunities. To cob this menace affecting SME's or reduced to the barest minimum, there is an urgent need for mass financial education of SME's operators, provision of modern ICT support, regulators to embark on compliance and regulatory drive and above all the provision of enabling environment for SME's to optimized.

FinTech companies support SMEs with innovative modern means of fast-tracking payments and transactions. Digital wallets, mobile payment systems, and point-of-sale (POS) technology make payment receipt safe and easy for businesses. This innovation reduces if not eliminate over dependence on cash transactions with it associated risks, f addition, cross-border payment is optimized with SMEs contributing to global trade while processing times and transactional costs are reduced maximally.

This study examined the impacts of financial technology on the performance of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria, by examining the roles of financial technology companies in addressing small and medium enterprises financial challenges, analyzing the benefits and risks associated with financial technology companies' adoption by Small and Medium Enterprises, and exploring future trends in financial technology companies for Small and Medium Enterprises.

Literature Review

Financial technology firms (FinTech) are modern organisations that employ technology to develop and improve existing financial systems and services. Fintech firms are known for digital products enabling sectors like banking, insurance, mortgage, wealth management and regulatory needs (Ogiriki and Atagboro 2022). They aim to enhance effectiveness and efficiency in the financial sector.

Financial technology companies use cutting-edge technologies in financial services and products. Mobile banking, online lending platforms, digital payment systems, robo-advisors, and blockchain-based applications like crypto currencies are just a few examples of the many technological developments in financial services that fall under this broad category. Startups and existing firms that seek to enhance, supplement, or replace conventional financial services are referred to as financial technology companies (Ahmed-Ishmel, Onyeiwu and Owopetu 2018).

.Key Characteristics of Fintech Companies include;

- i. Technological innovation: Faster automated transactions and emerging technologies such as data analytics, blockchain, cloud computing and artificial intelligence introduced.
- ii. Fintech companies change the narrative of traditional financial services, moving away from old method to a more affordable, convenient, and customized options that meet the demands of contemporary businesses and consumers.

- iii. Agility and Flexibility: Fintech companies as a matter of principle take feedbacks important such that they scale their businesses efficiently, innovate quickly and improve their products swiftly .
- iv. Fintech companies work with regulatory authorities, conform with laydown rules to ensure compliance to gain the trust of regulators, investors and customers .

Small Medium Enterprises

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of many economies around the world and play a significant role in employment creation, innovation and gross domestic product (GDP) growth. SMEs make up 90% of businesses and over 50% of employment globally. Despite their relevance, they suffer some setbacks that limit their growth (World Bank 2020).

The Role of SMEs in Economic Development:

The followings are some of the roles SMEs predominantly play in fostering economic development across nations of the world:

- i. Employment generation: SMEs accounts for the highest jobs generation across nations of the world, approximately 70% of jobs in developing nations are provided by SMEs (International Labour Organization 2019).
- ii. Innovation and Technological Development: SMEs promote innovation by launching novel goods , services and procedures. They often serve as breeding grounds for novel concepts and innovations in technology (Ogiriki and Atagboro 2022).
- iii. **GDP Contribution:** SMEs contribute to national income by enhancing production and export activities (OECD, 2017).

Challenges Facing SMEs Operations

Limited Finance Access: One of the most significant inhibitors that SMEs face is access to finance in limited amounts. Traditional financial institutions consider SMEs as risky credit borrowers (Beck et al., 2008).

Regulatory and bureaucratic constraints: SMEs are often faced with complying with laws and policies which could have an adverse effect on their profitability and sustainability (Djankov et al., 2002).

Market Competition: SMEs face fierce rivalry as a result of globalization and the existence of big multinational firms (Porter, 1990).

The Link Between Financial Companies and Small and Medium Enterprises

The relationship between fintech companies and SMEs, the benefits, challenges, and future prospects of this dynamic interaction are thus highlighted as follows.

Fintech companies serve as the bedrock bridging the financial gap, leveraging on

modern technology and providing financial support and services to small and medium-sized enterprises. SMEs are expedient to economic growth and employment creation, but they are often being doubted and reservations for them exist due to high risk, lack of credit history, and high transaction costs (Berger and Udell, 2006).

Financial Technology Company and Access to Finance

Financial technology companies significantly enhance access to financial services for small and medium enterprises. One of the major challenge SMEs faces is access to credit, stricter terms and conditions set by traditional banks are enormous making it difficult for SMEs to access credit. Fintech companies use alternative lending strategies like peer-to-peer (P2P), crowd sourcing and revenue-based financing, to solve the credit problem (Zhang et al., 2021). Fintech companies raised credit opportunities for SMEs via creditworthiness using non-traditional data sources through the use of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning and big data analytics, (Gomber et al., 2017). In my opinion, financial technology companies are the bloodline and financier of modern SME's businesses ensuring their growth and survival. Fintech companies are the risk takers, backbones, fund providers, and worthy entrepreneurs.

SME's Adoption of Financial Technology Solutions

The adoption of financial technology solutions has positively impacted small and medium enterprises, its financial performance and business growth. Fintech companies over the years have provided SMEs with digital payment platforms, reduce costs, improve cash flow management, and increase transaction efficiency (Arner et al., 2015). Fintech adoption by SMEs has largely assisted in obtaining quick financing without the strict requirements of traditional banks. This as often increases business liquidity and investment capacity.

Personal experiences with some SME's operators during the course of this study shows that adoption of financial technology solutions as immensely be a blessing for the SME's sector as faster, reliable, cheaper, and more efficient financial services are processed and delivered which improves their overall financial operations and business performance.

Emerging Financial Technologies and Financial Inclusion; A Blessings OR Curses to SME's Activities

Emerging financial technologies plays a significant role in small and medium enterprises with recourse to financial inclusion, x-raying both the positive impacts (blessing) and the negative implications (curse) of financial technology on SMEs will imperatively balance this concept.

Many small businesses before now collapsed due to lack of collateral or goodwill from our recognized traditional banks but now they can access funding through

crowdfunding and digital lending platforms. Digital payment systems allow SMEs to contribute and participate in e-commerce and international trade, increasing sales volume and expanding customer base. It also, allows for well managed financial applications, keeping adequate and accurate books of accounting records, cash flow system and general financial planning and forecasting.

Conveniently, SMEs can now process payments instantly and manage financial transactions efficiently and effectively.

(Philippon) 2016 opined that increased financial inclusion enables SMEs to participate in international markets without the limitations of traditional banking; in addition to financing, fintech solutions help SMEs streamline operations through automated invoicing, cloud-based accounting software, and real-time financial tracking. These innovations reduce administrative burdens, improve decision-making, improve financial transparency, and ultimately promoting business growth and sustainability.

However, this innovation presently has drawbacks which includes regulatory and compliance issues, system downtime and internet disruptions, above all is the menace of cybersecurity risk which has now become a global phenomenon. All these points in-view possess traits to SMEs and will definitely disrupt business activities. Thus, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) theory underpins this study; it was proposed by Davis (1989). The theory explains how users accept and use new technologies based on two key factors; Perceived Usefulness (belief that technology improves performance) and Perceived Ease of Use – belief that technology is easy to use. Its relevance to this study depicts that SMEs adopt FinTech solutions and its adoption influences firm performance.

Oyewale and Alabi (2024) investigated the influence of financial inclusion on SME performance in Osun State, Nigeria. Multiple regression analysis was employed to test the relationship between financial inclusion indicators and SME performance. The results revealed that financial inclusion significantly improved SME performance.

Ediri (2025) investigated the effect of financial technologies on SME performance in Nsukka, Enugu State. 301 SMEs were sampled and data analyzed with a logistic regression model.

The findings revealed that financial technologies such as digital payments, online banking, and automated financial tools significantly improved sales volume, profitability, and financial performance of SMEs. The study concluded that SMEs adopting financial technologies were more likely to achieve improved operational efficiency and financial sustainability.

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Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher Fieldwork 2026

The diagram above attempted to explain how FinTech companies influence Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) through access to financial services, financial performance, growth, and financial inclusion. It does propose three hypotheses (H₁, H₂, and H₃) that describe the relationships among the variables.

Thus, the framework suggests that FinTech companies play a crucial role in transforming SME development through three key pathways: Improving access to financial services, enhancing financial performance and business growth and promoting financial inclusion.

Sampling Technique

Methodology

The study adopted a quantitative survey research design, with descriptive and explanatory approaches, simple random sampling technique was employed to ensure that every SME within the defined population had an equal chance of selection, Data were collected through primary sources, specifically via the administration of structured questionnaires. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale, The instrument achieved content validity through expert evaluation, The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient in SPSS. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The analysis included frequencies, regression analysis and analysis of variance to determine the overall significance of the regression models

The population of the study consists of registered SME operators actively having access to financial technology services in selected commercial hubs in Ogun State,

Nigeria. According to Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) reports over 31,000 SMEs in Ogun State, not all are active, accessible and FinTech users. Therefore, the study narrows the population to accessible registered SMEs in major commercial areas such as (Abeokuta, Ijebu-Ode, Sagamu and Ota). The accessible and active SME population used for this study is 1,200 registered and active SME's operators. The sample size of 300 SME's was determined using the Yamane (1967) formula

Results

SMEs Profiling

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Business Sector		
- Retail	100	33.3%
- Manufacturing	80	26.7%
- Services	70	23.3%
- Technology	50	16.7%
FinTechAdoption		
- Yes	220	73.3%
- No	80	26.7%

Researcher Fieldwork, 2026.

Demographic Profile of SMEs Table 1 presents a descriptive summary of the small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) that took part in the research, highlighting two important variables: FinTech Adoption and Business Sector.

Distribution by Business Sector

The retail industry employs the bulk of SMEs examined, making up 33.3% (n=100) of the sample as a whole. Services (23.3%), manufacturing (26.7%), and technology (16.7%) come next. Although the sample appears to represent a wide variety of businesses, this distribution shows a minor bias toward more conventional industries like manufacturing and retail. Because different industries have different operational issues and financial needs, this could affect how FinTech solutions are viewed and accepted.

Adoption of FinTech

A significant percentage of SMEs (73.3%) reported utilizing FinTech services, while 26.7% argued that they had not adopted the technology. This high acceptance rate is indicative of an increasing trend in SMEs' use of digital financial services, which is probably being driven by elements like cost-effectiveness, accessibility, and the demand for financial innovation.

Regression analysis, which was utilized to evaluate hypotheses regarding the

influence of FinTech adoption possibly on financial access, corporate performance, or operational efficiency is bolstered by the comparatively large number of adopters. Thematic analysis of the qualitative replies can enhance this comprehension even more by illuminating the reasons behind adoption in various industries, as well as any perceived advantages or issues.

Regression Analysis Results

Hypothesis	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Beta Coefficient	p-value	Significance
H ₁	FinTech Adoption	Access to Financial Services	0.68	0.001	
H ₂	FinTech Usage Level	SME Financial Performance	0.52	0.003	
H ₃	Emerging Technologies	Financial Inclusion	0.59	0.002	

Significance level: $p < 0.05$

Table 2 presents the regression analysis results for three hypotheses (H₁, H₂, H₃) in relation to the impact of FinTech adoption, usage, and emerging technologies on financial outcomes. Each row tests a separate hypothesis with an independent variable (predictor), a dependent variable (outcome), a beta coefficient (strength and direction of the relationship), and a p-value (statistical significance).

Below is the breakdown of each hypothesis tested:

Hypothesis 1: FinTech and Access to Financial Services

SMEs that use digital payment systems, online banking, and alternative lending platforms report better cash flow management and increased access to capital, which is consistent with previous research showing that FinTech solutions lower financial barriers for SMEs. The results show that FinTech adoption significantly improves access to financial services for SMEs ($\beta = 0.68$, $p = 0.001$).

Hypothesis 2: FinTech Adoption and SME Financial Performance

FinTech adoption and better financial performance were found to be positively correlated ($\beta = 0.52$, $p = 0.003$). SMEs report increased revenue growth, profitability, and operational efficiency when they use peer-to-peer lending platforms, automated invoicing, and mobile banking. This implies that FinTech helps SMEs make better financial decisions and cut costs.

Hypothesis 3: Emerging Financial Technologies and SME Financial Inclusion

SMEs' access to finance ($\beta = 0.59$, $p = 0.002$). Digital wallets, blockchain, and AI-powered credit scoring are among the technologies that are filling in the holes in

conventional financial services. According to the survey, new financial technologies play a big role in helping SMEs get loans, handle transactions safely, and reach a wider audience.

ANOVA Results for Overall Model Significance

Model	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value
1	Regression	58.742	1	58.742	55.80	0.001
	Residual	313.558	298	1.052		
	Total	372.300	299			
2	Regression	42.116	1	42.116	38.32	0.003
	Residual	327.884	298	1.100		
	Total	370.000	299			
3	Regression	49.530	1	49.530	45.98	0.002
	Residual	321.470	298	1.079		
	Total	371.000	299			

$p < 0.01$

The ANOVA table (Table 3) provides insights into the overall significance of the regression model. The F-value and p-value determine whether the independent variables collectively explain a significant proportion of the variance in the dependent variable. Given the regression analysis results, the model appears to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming the positive impact of FinTech adoption, usage level, and emerging technologies on SME financial outcomes.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the impact of FinTech solutions on SMEs, particularly their influence on access to financial services, financial performance, and financial inclusion. The key findings are as follows:

FinTech Adoption and Access to Financial Services:

It was reviewed that the use of FinTech impacted SMEs' access to financial services ($\beta = 0.68$, $p = 0.001$). alternative lending platforms, online banking, and digital payment methods have made it easier to access resources and manage cash flow.

These results agreed with earlier studies that indicate FinTech solutions support SMEs in reducing financial obstacles (Zavolokina *et al.*, 2016; Philippon, 2016).

FinTech Adoption and SME Financial Performance:

FinTech adoption and SME financial performance were significantly positively correlated ($\beta = 0.52$, $p = 0.003$). SMEs that used and mobile banking, peer-to-peer lending platforms, automated invoicing, reported operational efficiency and higher revenue growth. These findings agreed with previous research that highlights cost-cutting advantages and the financial decision-making of FinTech for SMEs (Gomber *et al.*, 2017; Chen and Bellavitis, 2020).

Emerging Financial Technologies and Financial Inclusion:

The study discovered that SME financial inclusion is influenced by new financial technology ($\beta = 0.59$, $p = 0.002$). Technological advancements like blockchain, digital wallets, and AI-powered credit scoring have increased SMEs' access to financing. The findings of Arner *et al.* (2020), which emphasize how digital financial solutions foster inclusion, are consistent with this.

In Conclusion the results show that FinTech is an essential tool for the expansion of SMEs, company performance and financial accessibility. Financial inclusion, financial performance, and easier access to financial services are all experienced by SMEs that uses financial digital instruments. The study emphasizes that FinTech has the ability to significantly improve SME competitiveness and resilience. The study recommends that financial institutions and FinTech companies should work together to raise the financial literacy of SMEs operators and provide them with the required skills to effectively optimized. In addition, regulatory framework should be developed to guarantee the safe and equitable use of FinTech by SMEs. Regulators should set clear policies; while safeguarding the interests of SMEs, governments should endeavor to pave an enabling environment that encourages innovation. Similarly, prioritizing investments in digital infrastructure will improve access to FinTech services, particularly in rural areas and enable safe financial transactions, cybersecurity and dependable internet connectivity should be reinforced.

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